

The Effect of 1%, 2% and 4% Sucrose Induction on Zebrafish Cardiomyocyte Damage

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Abstract

One of the complications of diabetes is cardiovascular disease. Some studies mention insulin resistance in the cardiac muscle will increase the occurrence of inflammation and necrosis of cardiac muscle cells. The study aims to prove the effect of sucrose induction on zebrafish cardiomyocyte damage. The research was conducted in the laboratory, using a post test group control design. The research sample used zebra fish. The research group consisted of normal control group (N) and sucrose induction group 1% (G1), 2% (G2) and 4% (G3). Hyperglycemia induction is a modification of previous researchers. The process of inducing 1%, 2%, 4% sucrose in zebrafish bath water for 28 days which is replaced every 2 days. The treatment process followed laboratory procedures. At the end of the study, zebrafish were fed for 10 hours, then anesthetized by placing the fish in ice water for 10 minutes. Furthermore, blood glucose levels were measured through the tail using glucotest. Normal glucose levels of zebrafish are between 40-90 mg/dL. Cardiac organ was taken and histology prepare was made. Cardiac damage in the form of leukocyte infiltration and the area of cardiac muscle cell edema was calculated histologically, with HE staining, 400 x magnification, using image J software. Measurement data were analyzed using ONEWAY ANOVA, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The average percentage of leukocyte cell infiltration of G3 was 40% higher than N (15%), G1 (19%) and G2 (27%) with $p < 0.05$. G3 odem area of (42%) was greater than the normal group N (5%), G1 (18%) and G2 (34%) with $p < 0.05$. It is suspected that this condition is due to the effect of hyperglycemia due to the induction of 4% sucrose (179mg/dL). From this study it can be concluded that 4% glucose induction causes damage to zebrafish heart cells which is characterized by the presence of leukocyte cell infiltration of 40% and odem area of 42%.

Keywords: Zebrafish, sucrose, cardiomyocyte

Introduction

Sucrose is a disaccharide composed of α -D- glucopyranosyl and β -D-fructofuranosyl that binds between its reducing ends. Sucrose has no reducing end so it is included in non-reducing sugars [1]. A diet high in sucrose can lead to elevated glucose levels, as excessive sucrose will be metabolized in the liver into fat rather than glycogen. This can lead to lower glucose utilization by tissues so that blood glucose levels increase and trigger insulin resistance [2]. In addition, research by (Haq *et al*, 2022) also states that the induction of fructose and high fat in rats for 10 weeks resulted in increased damage to the heart[3].

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a chronic disease characterized by blood glucose levels exceeding normal, namely blood sugar levels during equal or more than 200 mg/dl, and fasting blood sugar levels above or equal to 126 mg/dl [4]. Common complaints of DM patients include weakness, tingling, itching, blurred eyes, and erectile dysfunction in men, and itching in the genital area in women.

The prevalence of DM in the world based on IDF is 1.9% and has made DM the seventh leading cause of death in the world. Indonesia alone ranks fourth in the number of people with DM after the United States, China, and India. According to WHO data, DM sufferers in the world amounted to 171 million in 2015[6].

Hyperglycemia is a condition where the body's cells are unable to respond fully to insulin, or impaired insulin secretory function [5]. Hyperglycemia also induces the production of Reactive Oxydative Species (ROS) which increases oxidative stress, thereby causing aberrant gene expression, impaired signal transduction and activation of pathways that lead to programmed cardiac muscle cell death or apoptosis, inflammatory cell infiltration and interstitial edema [7]. Inflammation results in the

release of mediators that cause vasodilation, increase microvascular permeability and induce leukocyte infiltration. Relaxation of vascular smooth muscle cells in arterioles and precapillary sphincters results in decreased resistance, thus increasing capillary pressure. This leads to edema in the interstitium [8].

Zebrafish have proven useful for modeling human heart disease due to their similarity to the mammalian heart, their rapid and manageable development, and the genetic methods available. Embryonic heart development is rapid and cardiac function is easily observed [9].

Research conducted by Glesson et al., 2007 showed that zebrafish exposed to 1% and 2% solutions for 24 hours resulted in increased blood glucose levels [10]. In addition, research conducted by Singh et al., 2019 resulted in a decrease in the ability to change the rate of glucose transport where zebrafish were exposed to a 4% glucose solution [11]. Research by Xiao et al., 2021 states that zebrafish exposed to 2,6-Dichloro-1,4-benzoquinone at doses of 0.25, 0.5, and 1 μm for 4 days causes histological changes in the zebrafish heart such as cardiomyocyte hemorrhage, interstitial edema, myocardial cell necrosis, and myofiber damage [12]. Inflammation occurs because prolonged hyperglycemia conditions trigger the accumulation of AGEs which results in endothelial cells and monocytes producing inflammatory mediators in large quantities [13]. In addition, interstitial edema in the heart muscle occurs due to increased vascular pressure that is higher than the filtration capacity of the lymphatic capillaries [14].

Based on the facts mentioned above, further research was conducted related to the pattern of hyperglycemia in zebrafish as a test model due to sucrose induction. This study was conducted by validating previous research, namely with 1%, 2%, and 4% sucrose induction on interstitial edema and inflammatory cell infiltration of zebrafish heart muscle (*Danio rerio*) for 28 days.

Material and Methods

Design, Place and Time of Research

The research was conducted at the Fish Cultivation Laboratory, Division of Fish Reproduction, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science (FPIK), Brawijaya University, Malang for the stages of maintenance, actuation, fish dissection, and heart organ harvesting. While the preparation stage (dehydration, soaking, printing, cutting, staining, mounting), observation and scoring of inflammatory cell infiltration and interstitial edema area were carried out at the Anatomical Pathology and Histology Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang. This study was conducted from August 2023 to January 2024. This research has had a letter of Ethical Decency with No.077/LE.003/X/03/2023. The zebrafish was then determined at the Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Sciences, Universitas Airlangga with determination number 71/UMLKILP/UA.FPK/12/2023.

Animal Treatment

The samples in this study were zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), males measuring 3-5 cm aged 4-5 months in healthy condition and not deformed. Zebrafish were obtained from the Fish Cultivation Laboratory, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science (FPIK), Universitas Brawijaya, Malang. This study consisted of 4 groups: normal group (N), 1% sucrose induction group (G1), 2% sucrose induction group (G2), and 4% sucrose induction group (G3). Each group consisted of 30 zebrafish with 5 replicates in 2 aquariums containing 2L of water. Induction water was changed every 2 days to avoid the growth of bacteria or other microorganisms [15].

Zebrafish were acclimatized for 1 week under constant laboratory conditions with a temperature of 28°C, 14 hours of lighting, 10 hours of dark illumination, feed, and water. Feeding is 3 times every day, namely morning, afternoon, and evening. After the acclimatization process, sucrose induction was carried out for 28 days in experimental animals. Furthermore, at the end of the treatment on day 29 the zebrafish were fed for 12 hours before surgery. After that the zebrafish were euthanized using cold water for 10 minutes. Then after the fish is unconscious, the fish is sacrificed on the board and then surgery is performed to take the zebrafish heart organ. Furthermore, the heart organ was blocked with paraffin for histology preparation and HE staining.

Preparation of Heart Muscle Histology Preparations with Hematoxylin Eosin (HE) Staining

The initial stage of making this preparate is done by soaking the heart organ in 10% phosphate buffered formalin for 24 hours. After soaking, the heart organ was then sliced with a thickness of ± 3 mm so that it could be inserted into the cassette for processing in a tissue processor. The heart organ in the cassette was dehydrated using 70%, 80, and 96% alcohol for 2 hours. The tissue was then clarified by putting the cassette into xylol I, xylol II, and xylol III.

After the purification process, the tissue was put into liquid paraffin at 56 °C for 2 hours twice. Next, the tissue was taken with tweezers and then blocked with paraffin. The tissue that has been blocked is then cut using a microtome with a thickness of 4-5 µm. The cut tissue was developed on water in a waterbath and captured with an object glass. Then the tissue was dried at room temperature for further staining with Hematoxylin Eosin (HE). After staining, the preparate was dried and mounted using glue [16].

Calculation of the Number of Inflammatory Cell Infiltration of Zebra Fish Heart Muscle (*D. rerio*)

Heart muscle preparations that have been prepared and HE staining are then observed with an OLYMPUS BX53M Trinocular Microscope with a magnification of 400x. Reading the preparation on the microscope in 10 different fields of view starting from the left edge, then down to the bottom and back shifted zigzag. After that, the images were taken and then manually counted the number of inflammatory cell infiltrations in each field of view. This calculation was done by 3 different observers and from different fields of view. The calculation of inflammatory cell infiltration uses the following formula:

$$(\%) = \frac{a}{b} \times 100\%$$

Proportion of inflammatory cell infiltration calculation Description: a = The number of inflammatory cell infiltrations in 1 field of view. b = Total number of cells in 1 field of view.

Calculation of Interstitial Edema Area of Zebra Fish Heart Muscle (*D. rerio*)

Heart muscle preparations have been prepared and HE staining is then observed with an OLYMPUS BX53A Trinocular Microscope with 200x magnification. Furthermore, the preparation was photographed and transferred to the Image J application to further measure the area that experienced interstitial edema. Calculations were made with 3 different observers and from different fields of view which were then averaged to get the total results. Calculation in the ImageJ application uses the binary menu to select the area you want to measure, then with the measure menu to get the results of the measured area [17].

Data Analysis Technique

Observation data were analyzed using SPSS 26.0. Initial data were analyzed descriptively and then processed with the Shapiro-wilk test to determine the normality and homogeneity of the data. After that, One Way Anova statistical test was carried out for differences between groups with a significance degree of $p < 0.05$. The results of the comparison between each group after the One Way ANOVA test if there is significance then continued using the Tukey test.

Results and Data Analysis

Animal Characteristics

The characteristics of the experimental animals can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Animal characteristics

Description	Normal (N)	Induction 1 (G1)	Induction 2% (G2)	Induction4 (G3)
1. Animal Testing	Zebrafish	Zebrafish	Zebrafish	Zebrafish
2. Number of Animals	30	30	30	30
3. Gender	Male	Male	Male	Male
4. Body weight	3,4 gram	2,8 gram	2,8 gram	2,6 gram
5. Age	Adult Phase (4-5 months)	Adult Phase (4-5 months)	Adult Phase (4-5 months)	Adult Phase (4-5 months)
1. Induction	No induction, only 2L of water in the aquarium.	1% sucrose dissolved in 2L of water in an aquarium	2% sucrose dissolved in 2L of water in an aquarium	4% sucrose dissolved in 2L of water in an aquarium
2. Duration of Induction	28 days	28 days	28 days	28 days
3. Water Change	Once every 2 days	Once every 2 days	Once every 2 days	Once every 2 days

Effect of Sucrose Induction on Infiltration of Zebrafish Heart Muscle Cells (*D. rerio*)

The results of the calculation of inflammatory cell infiltration can be seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1. Histopathology of Inflammatory Cell Infiltration of Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) Heart Muscle with HE Staining and 400x Magnification

Description: N : Normal Group, G1: 1% Sucrose Induction Group, G2: 2% Sucrose Induction Group, G3: 4% Sucrose Induction Group. Black Arrows: Normal cardiomyocyte nuclei, Yellow arrows: Inflammatory cell infiltration.

Figure 2. Histogram of the Average Number of Inflammatory Cell Infiltration of Zebrafish Heart Muscle (*D. rerio*) After Sucrose Induction for 28 days

Description: N : Normal Group, G1: 1% Induction Group, G2: 2% Induction Group, G3: 4% Induction Group. * a, b, c... = different letters indicate significant differences (p<0,05)

The results showed that sucrose induction caused an increase in the number of inflammatory cell infiltration compared to N p<0.05. The increase in the number of inflammatory cell infiltration of

zebrafish (*D. rerio*) was 19%, 27%, 40% in groups G1, G2, G3 compared to the control. Between treatment groups, it was found that N was not different from P1 but significantly different from G2 and G3. The higher the dose, the greater the percentage of the number of cells that experience inflammatory cell infiltration.

Effect of Sucrose Induction on the Area of Interstitial Edema of Zebra Fish Heart Muscle (*D. rerio*)

The results of the calculation of interstitial edema area can be seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3. Histopathology of Interstitial Edema Area of Zebrafish Heart Muscle with 400x Magnification and HE Staining

Description: N: Normal Group, G1: 1% Induction Group, G2: 2% Induction Group, G3: 4% Induction Group. Red arrow: area of edema.

Figure 4 Histogram of Mean Area of Interstitial Edema of Zebrafish Heart Muscle (*D. rerio*) after Sucrose Induction at 28 days

Description: N: Normal Group, G1: 1% Induction Group, G2: 2% Induction Group, G3: 4% Induction Group. * a, b, c... = different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0,05$)

The results showed that sucrose induction caused an increase in the area of interstitial edema compared to the normal group. The increase in interstitial edema area of zebrafish heart muscle (*D. rerio*) was 18%, 34%, 42% in groups G1, G2, G3 compared to the control. Between treatment groups, it was found that N was significantly different compared to G1, G2, and G3. The higher the dose, the greater the percentage of edematous area.

Discussion

Animal Characteristics

This study used Zebra Fish (*D. rerio*) as the research sample. Zebrafish has many advantages and is suitable to be used as an animal model of hyperglycemia. Various advantages such as mammalian-like pancreas specifications [18], having a major organ system, such as a beating heart, mammalian-like glucose regulation [19], and similarities of nearly 70% of human genes [20].

Determination of the number of samples is based on the 1991 Federer formula, which from the calculation obtained the results of 6 heads. Each treatment consists of 5 replicates so that each treatment consists of 30 zebrafish. The number of samples used is to avoid sampling error in the study.

This study showed a decrease in body weight of zebrafish after 1%, 2%, and 4% sucrose induction. This weight loss is a metabolic disorder associated with diabetes and pancreatic beta cell damage. This is in line with research (Shovit et al., 2010) which states that zebrafish induced by sucrose solution will result in a decrease in body weight of zebrafish that have been induced compared to normal zebrafish [21].

The zebrafish used in the study were 4-5 months old. This age selection is significant with research (Victoria et al., 2016) which states that zebrafish aged 4-11 months are preferred to be used in the induction method using glucose solution compared to zebrafish aged 1-3 years [22]. Furthermore, the use of sucrose in this study also refers to previous research which states that diets that are very high in sucrose cause many metabolic disorders, such as obesity, insulin resistance, glucose intolerance, and dyslipidemia.

This study showed an increase in blood glucose levels after being induced with 1%, 2%, and 4% sucrose for 28 days in a 2L aquarium. The results of this study are in line with the research of Eriko et. al, which states that a high-sucrose diet in rats causes an increase in glucose levels in rats fed a high-sucrose diet compared to normal rats.

Infiltration of Inflammatory Cells in the Heart Muscle of Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) After Sucrose Induction of 1%, 2%, and 4% for 28 days.

This study proves that the induction of 1%, 2%, and 4% sucrose induction causes infiltration of inflammatory cells in the heart muscle of zebrafish. The higher the level of sucrose induced causes the higher the number of inflammatory cell infiltration. This is in line with research which shows that if the dose of sucrose induced by the exposure given is greater, it will cause stress conditions in rats that trigger disturbances in controlling blood sugar levels, causing blood sugar levels to increase [23]. This increase in blood sugar levels will trigger accumulation of Advanced Glycation-End Products (AGEs) which causes endothelial cells and monocytes to produce inflammatory mediators in large quantities [13]. The results of research conducted by (Salsabil, 2024) showed that sucrose induction of 2% and 4% increased fasting blood glucose levels by 25% and 35% [24].

Hyperglycemic conditions will trigger an increase in Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS), which will lead to the activation of Poly (ADP-Ribose) Polymerase (PARP) through Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) breakdown. This activation of PARP will result in inhibition of Glyceraldehyde-3-Phosphate Dehydrogenase (GAPDH) and result in an increase in the polyol and hexosamine pathways. The increase in these pathways can lead to increased non-enzymatic glycation, excessive production of AGEs, oxidative stress, and Diacylglycerol (DAG) synthesis, which will activate Protein Kinase C (PKC). This activated PKC will activate nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) to stimulate pro-inflammatory genes to secrete inflammatory mediators, such as Tumor Necrosis Factor- α (TNF- α) and Interleukin -1 β (IL- 1 β) [13].

In addition, following inflammation, the innate immune response is activated through recognition by Toll-Like Receptor (TLR), Pathogen-associated molecular pattern molecules (PAMPs), and Damage-Associated Molecular Pattern Molecules (DAMPs). Activated innate immune cells and cardiac cells release cytokines, chemokines, interferons, and alarmin, leading to further activation and placement of innate immune cells into the heart, including mast cells, neutrophils, dendritic cells, monocytes, and macrophages. Excessive or persistent activation of the innate immune system can lead to excessive

and/or chronic inflammatory processes that trigger myocardial damage and remodeling, culminating in cardiac dysfunction [25].

Between treatment groups, it was found that N was not different from G1 but significantly different from G2 and G3 ($P < 0,05$). The higher the dose, the greater the percentage of the number of cells that experience inflammatory cell infiltration. This is in line with research (Stumvol, 2005) which shows that if the dose of exposure given is greater, it will cause stress conditions in rats that trigger disturbances in controlling blood sugar levels, causing blood sugar levels to increase. This increase in blood sugar levels will trigger the accumulation of AGEs which results in endothelial cells and monocytes producing inflammatory mediators in large quantities [23].

Area of Interstitial Edema of Zebrafish Heart Muscle (*D. rerio*) After Sucrose Induction for 28 days.

This study shows that the normal group has an interstitial edema area that is significantly different from the 1%, 2%, and 4% sucrose induction groups. Exposure to higher doses of sucrose will cause an increase in edema area. This is in line with Haq's research 2022 which states that high fructose diets and high fat diets will cause lipid accumulation and increased oxidative stress [3]. Increased *Reactive Oxygen Species* (ROS) production will lead to the formation of atherosclerotic lesions through several pathways, namely the *Protein Kinase C* (PKC) activation pathway, activation of the polyol and hexosamine pathways, accumulation of AGEs with increased expression of the Receptor for Advanced Glycation End Products (RAGE). In general, superoxide ions will react with NO to form peroxynitrite, an oxidant that inhibits prostacyclin (PGI₂). This decrease in PGI₂ triggers an increase in endoperoxides (PGH₂) resulting in endothelial dysfunction. [26].

Research by Schochet and Jialal (2023) states that in a state of endothelial dysfunction there is an increase in endothelial permeability where the permeability of the capillary wall increases which results in increased capillary filtration. In addition, the protein coefficient in the capillary wall decreases, narrowing the difference between capillary oncotic pressure and oncotic pressure under the endothelial glycocalyx. The imbalance of high vascular flow by the filtration capacity of lymphatic capillaries causes edema.

Between treatment groups, there was a significant difference between G1, G2, and G3. The higher the dose, the greater the percentage of edema area. This is because there is an increase in vascular pressure that is higher than the filtration capacity of lymphatic capillaries which causes an abnormal increase in interstitial fluid resulting in edema.

Conclusions and Suggestions

4% Sucrose induction for 28 days is the best dose that results in an increase in the number of inflammatory cell infiltration by 40% and the area of interstitial edema by 42% of zebrafish heart muscle (*D. rerio*) compare N group.

The success of this study makes zebrafish (*D. rerio*) an animal model of hyperglycemia, then in the future research can be developed to test the effectiveness of an active compound from herbs that has the potential to reduce blood glucose levels, inhibit inflammatory cell infiltration and interstitial edema of zebrafish heart muscle (*D. rerio*) induced by 4% sucrose.

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